

Some fragments and development dynamics of the Georgian school of metapolitology of the III-XVIII centuries

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Abstract

For the first time, the Georgian school of political studies (metapolitology) is presented as a complex dynamic system existing since the 3rd century. Methodological framework of the research is based on the concept of metapolitology, where political studies (unlike other national schools) are presented with a syncretic model of scientific and non-scientific knowledge. The „inclusive design approach” is also utilized, which ensures the use of other sciences for political research and political practice. The concept of metapolitology is one of the pillars of metacognitive management that considers the use of various types of cognition to solve one problem.

Key words: political studies; political practice; metapolitology; metacognition

Introduction. To this day, the creation of Georgian political science is associated with A. Amilakhvari (1750-1805). However, according to the authors, this date is connected with (at least) the establishment of the Academy of Phasis in 274 - the existence of the Kolkheti

School of Rhetoric. The article presents other important examples of political studies and practice (metapolitology) in the III-XVIII centuries section.

Metapolitology is considered within the holistic model of the unified RTI ECA system of the metacognition: **political: Research (R)** - creation or transfer of new (scientific and non-scientific) knowledge-novation; **Technologies (T)**; **Innovation (I)** (introduction of innovation into practice); **Education (E)**; **Culture (C)**; updating of the **Administration (A)**. Metacognitive management of the research process provides an opportunity to restore knowledge that has been underestimated to this day [1; 2]. Metapolitology is considered metascience [3], which represents the possibility of pragmatic application of art and scientific knowledge [4]. According to the theory of metacognitive management, the whole spectrum of cognition is considered the experience, tradition, values, myth, faith, intuition, art and others.

The inclusive design of metapolitological studies derived from the principles of knowledge and cognitive economy - in addition to (political philosophy, political theory, comparative studies, international relations), discusses politics in the spectrum of other sciences: history, law, education, culture, administration, psychology, sociology, geography, cartography, toponymy, linguistics, mythology, theology, hagiography. Also, the Georgian school has always used methods and tricks of **political art** that were in no way inferior to the results obtained by applying scientific knowledge in practice (folklore, poetry, prose, painting, theater, drama, humor and satire, fables, wine-symposium etc.) to achieve political influence [2]. The article reflects examples of poly-role portraits of figures.

The Georgian nobleman, representative of the opposition to Erekle II, **Alexander Amilakhvari** in order to achieve influence simultaneously used the pamphlet of political

historiography - „Georgian History “, the political treatise „Sage of the East” and the dramaturgical scene „In Astrakhan“. Amilakhvari is represented as a **political figure**, criticist, pamphletist, theoretician, translator, playwright.

In 1776, **Gaios Rector** (1746-1821) translated and commented on the Greek writer Agapite Archdeacon (VI century) „Royal Charter or Sack “. Gaios Rector (unlike A. Amilakhvari), presents the opinion of the foreign author about what an ideal king should be to King Erekle II with great trepidation. Poly-role portrait of Gaios Rector: political and ecclesiastical figure, administrator, rector, missionary, supplicant, rhetorician, writer, teacher, translator, commentator, advisor, diplomat, administrator, orator, a specialist in Christian rhetoric, theologian [5].

Timothe Gabashvili (1703-1764) laid the foundation for studies of political toponymy and political identity. Researched the history of the origin of the name „Georgia” and also the common Iberian identity of Georgians and Spaniards. His applied research outside the borders of Georgia is an example of Georgian political culturology, cultural diplomacy and church diplomacy. In 1737, he compiled a polyfunctional relief map of Likhn-Imereti. Timothe Gabashvili's poly-role portrait is supplicant, archbishop, public figure and statesman, educator, advisor, diplomat, geographer, cartographer, writer, linguist, specialist of onomastics, and artist.

The work of **Vakhushti Batonishvili** (1696 – 1757) goes beyond the borders of Georgia and he is recognized as a world-class scientist. As the famous French orientalist Marie Brose writes in the XIX century: „*Vakhushti described his homeland as no Asian country has been described, except China...*“. His first atlas was created in 1735. Vakhushti Batonishvili’s poly-role portrait is mentor, enlightener, historiographer, geographer, cartographer,

toponymicist, linguist, heraldist and also caucasiologist, ethnographer, church and cultural diplomat and border researcher. .

In 1723, „Map of the Caucasus and the Caspian Sea” was published in Paris, co-authored by **Sulkhan-Saba Orbeliani** (1658-1725). In addition to prose, he used the fable genre, and in his collection „Wisdom of Lies“, humor and satire are directed at the king, viziers and demos. The lexicon created by him also represents the political technology of binding the nation together; promotes political communication between layers of society; development of science and education. His diplomatic work is also invaluable. His poly-role portrait is a political figure, educator, advisor, supplicant, diplomat, linguist, writer, prose writer, satirist, humorist.

Attention is drawn to the first map of Georgia created by **King Archil II** (1647-1713) in 1703. His works - „Sakartvelos Zneobani“, „Gaabaseba Katsisa da Soplisa“, „Mepeta Sakebelni da Samkhilebelni” „Sakebelni da Sakvedrebelni Ghmrtismshoblisani“, „Gaabaseba Teimurazisa da Rustvelisa”, „Leksni Aseulni”, „Leksni Asdaatni”(„Morals of Georgia“, „Conversation on Man and World“, „Praises and Revelations of Kings“, „Praiseworthy and Supplicants of the Mother of God“, „Conversations of Teimuraz and Rustveli“, „ Hundred Poems“, „Hundred and ten Poems“), represent great value and fill his poly-role portrait of a statesman (king), educator, historiographer, cartographer, theologian, axiologist [6].

Shota Rustaveli's „The Knight in the Panther's Skin“ is of special interest to metapolitology. „Tamar, to whom „The Knight in the Panther's Skin“ is dedicated not only portrayed as „Godly“, but also is mentioned as „similar to Christ“ and „Christ-blessed ruler“; That is, the concept of Christ-centered royal authority, which E.Kantorowicz has introduced into science,

in this work coexists alongside the God-centered royal government in general“ [7, 8, 9]. The poly-role portrait of Shota Rustaveli is a thinker, reviver, utopian, humanist, anthropocentrist, Christian monarchist, poet, theologian, axiologist, royal treasurer (“Mechurchletukhutsesi” – office of royal treasurer in medieval Georgia).

Giorgi Merchule's work should be of interest to specialists in political and canonical law, especially his views on the legal regulations of relations between the state and the church. „Merchule“ is a name denoting a profession and means a specialist in canonical law, a bishop of justice [10]. In 951, he dedicated a hagiographic work [11] to Grigol Khandzteli (Gregory of Khandzta), which represents a research direction of **political hagiography** as a subsystem of political theology. Early Church Fathers and representatives of the church in general had a great influence on political figures and political decisions. Grigol Khandzteli had such a strong influence that the representatives of the highest secular and church authorities used to obey his will.

Political hagiography discusses the study of prayer - as a type of political rhetoric. In Kartli's Tskhovreba (The Georgian Chronicle) a unique scene of the common prayer of King Archil I, King Mir, and King Leon is described in the VIII century Cathedral of Anakopia, in front of the hand-made icon of the Mother of God - before the battle with the Arabs, which is still of great interest for the research of wars and peace. Therefore, we cannot fail to gratefully mention **Leonti Mroveli**, **Juansher** and **other** unfortunately unknown co-authors in our „scientific prayer.“

The unique direction of research is the struggle of Christianity against pagan cultures. Therefore, in the IV-V centuries, such a tool of political struggle as the **science of Christian oratorical art**, the founder of which is considered to be **Saint John Chrysostom**, appears in the heart of religious organizations. A prominent example of this era is presented in the essay

„For the Reign of Justinian“, by the Greek historian Agathias Scholasticus (536-582), where the fact of the brutal murder of King Gubaz in 554 and the words of conversation spoken by the scholars of the Academy of Phasis - **Aiet and Phartaz** is presented - who were supposed to influence the political choice of Colchis - the coreligionist murderers of King Gubazi - the Byzantines or the fire-worshipper Persians? [12]. This event confirms the participation of scholars (scientists) of this era in Georgian politics, which confirms the fact of the real use of metacognitive monitoring in VI-century Georgia.

It should also be noted that rhetoric has always enjoyed special honor in traditions of Georgian thought and politics, which was well reflected in the tradition of the Georgian table-symposium.

Conclusion: the research proved that the Georgian school of applied politics (research, technology, innovation, education, culture and administration) – metapolitology existed (at least since the III century), which is represented by political: rhetoric, oratory, historiography, translation, theology, hagiography, axiology, geography, cartography, linguistics, onomastics, law. Also, with cultural, ecclesiastical and academic (scientific) diplomacy, war and peace studies, analysis, evaluation, criticism, commentary and diverse political art genres, which is confirmed by the poly-role portraits of public figures.

The centuries-old history of the Georgian Metapolitological School requires a new perception, a systematic description according to the stages of development of world science and a worthy representation in the unified international system of other national schools.

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აბსტრაქტი

სტატიაში პირველადაა წარმოდგენილი პოლიტიკის კვლევების (მეტაპოლიტოლოგიის) ქართული სკოლა, როგორც მე-III საუკუნიდან არსებული რთული ტიპის დინამიური სისტემა. კვლევის მეთოდოლოგიური საფუძველი ეყრდნობა მეტაპოლიტოლოგიის კონცეპციას, რომელშიც პოლიტიკური კვლევები (განსხვავებით სხვა ეროვნული სკოლებისაგან) წარმოდგენილია სამეცნიერო და არასამეცნიერო ცოდნის სინკრეტული მოდელით. გამოყენებულია ასევე „ინკლიუზიური დიზაინის მიდგომა“, რომელიც უზრუნველყოფს სხვა მეცნიერებათა გამოყენებას პოლიტიკის კვლევებისა და პოლიტიკური პრაქტიკისათვის. მეტაპოლიტოლოგიის კონცეპცია წარმოადგენს მეტაკოგნიტიური მართვის ერთ-ერთ საყრდენს და ითვალისწინებს ერთი პრობლემის მოგვარებისთვის შემეცნების სხვადასხვა სახეობათა გამოყენებას.

საკვანძო სიტყვები: პოლიტიკის კვლევები; პოლიტიკური პრაქტიკა; შემეცნება; მეტაშემეცნება

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